

Tax Aggressiveness and Financial Distress Likelihood: Does Board Equity Ownership Matter?

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates whether board ownership influences the dynamics between tax aggressiveness and financial distress likelihood of non-financial listed firms in Nigeria. This is against the backdrop of paucity of literature on this issue in the country. While financial distress was measured using the Altman's Z-score model, cash effective tax rate was used as a surrogate for tax aggressiveness. Based on data collected from the audited annual reports of 59 non-financial firms listed on the floor of the Nigeria Exchange Group (NGX) for the period 2013 to 2022, results of the moderated logistic regression technique revealed that tax aggressiveness exerts a positive and significant effect on financial distress. These results stressed the fact that managers may become more aggressive in their tax planning activities in order to improve cash flows which may subtly be a temporary bailout tool from distress. However, when board ownership was introduced as a moderator, the results of the study suggested a reversal experience for the financial status of the firms, signifying that tax aggressive firms with relatively higher board ownership policy will most likely be plunged into financial distress. This means that the marginal effect of increasing board ownership poses a serious concern for the financial position of firms that practice tax aggressiveness. Therefore, we recommend, amongst others, that relevant tax authorities and tax regulatory bodies may need to develop indicators for detecting financial distress likelihood in firms since managers of such firms may be tempted to evade taxes, ultimately lowering government tax revenue.

Keywords: *Tax aggressiveness, financial distress, logistic regression, non-finance listed firms*

1. Introduction

Corporate taxes are widely relied upon by governments across the globe to generate revenue for providing important public services such as security, infrastructures, and social amenities. On the other hand, corporate taxpayers usually strive to reduce their tax liabilities by using both legitimate and illegitimate means to evade tax payments, leading to fall in tax revenue in many countries (Annuar, Salihu, & Sheikh Obid, 2014; Fernández, García, Martínez, 2019). Firms regard taxes as significant costs because a portion of their earnings is deducted without clear and immediate compensation, whereas tax avoidance increases net cash flows, which can be used to finance corporate investments, share buybacks or be distributed to shareholders as dividends (Jihene & Moez, 2019).

Ideally, firms should adopt a balanced tax reporting position that assesses tax savings against the expected direct and indirect costs of tax aggressiveness. But, when the difficulties faced in accessing external funds increase, financially distressed firms can resort to using different strategies directed at preserving internal finance for future investment opportunities and reduce the negative effects of the financial difficulties. One potential internal source of financing that has received little attention until recent years is tax aggressiveness. Hanlon and Heitzman (2010) described (aggressive) tax avoidance as a range with legitimate tax planning on one end and illegitimate tax evasion on the other end. Despite the risks associated with the practice, Desai and Dharmapala, (2009) considered tax aggressive actions as having greater benefits than costs since higher profits could lead to higher returns to investors and larger firm value. Yusuf & Abudulkarim (2021) perceived financial distress as a situation in which a firm is unable to generate adequate earnings that can sustain its operating and financing activities, which then incapacitates the firm from meeting its financial obligations to lenders.

There are studies that have investigated how firms can use tax aggressiveness as a source of funding for their investment opportunities in response to greater financial distress. For instance, Law and Mills (2015) demonstrated why financially-distressed firms will aggressively practice tax avoidance especially when financial pressure and risk of bankruptcy are high enough. Brondolo (2009) affirmed tax savings made via tax aggressiveness as funds by firms in financial difficulties are used to support current operations, honour debt covenants and lessen the risk of bankruptcy and likelihood of financial distress. However, studies that have explored the potentially moderating effect of board ownership on the link between tax aggressiveness and financial distress are sparse.

The objective of this study, therefore, is to fill this gap in the literature by analysing whether the effect of tax aggressiveness on financial distress is moderated by board equity ownership, while exploring the dynamics between tax aggressiveness and financial distress using Nigeria as a reference point. Interestingly, the moderating effect of board ownership on the link between tax aggressiveness and financial distress has not been investigated within the context of Nigeria.

The remaining part of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 focuses on literature review and hypotheses development. Following this section is section 3 which addresses the methodology employed in this study, comprising the research design, sample, measurement and operationalisation of variables. The result of data analysis and discussions are presented in section 4, while section 5 concludes the study with some recommendations

2. Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Literature

2.1.1 Financial Distress

Generally, a situation where a company's cash flow is insufficient to cover its debt obligations sets in financial distress. The above definition can be linked to that of Ehab, Rahim, and Ananth (2011) who opined that financial distress is the state in which a borrower is unable to meet financial obligations. When financial problems are unchecked, it can lead to bankruptcy, delisting, or organisational restructuring (Muller, Steyn-Bruwer & Hamman, 2009). Following prior related studies, two key potential causes of financial distress have been identified: failure of credit institutions and financial creditors to foresee and prevent financial distress situations, as well as their disregard for the significance of the effectiveness of corporate governance mechanisms in constraining financial distress (Husson-Traore, 2009).

Amendola, Restaino and Sensini (2015) stated that liquidation, inactiveness and bankruptcy could be activated due to legal form. Avramov, Chordia, Jostova, and Philipov (2013) noted that credit rating downgrades could be a warning sign of a firm's conditions, raising concerns about its future financial performance. Therefore, such situations may tempt businesses to pursue risky and aggressive tax avoidance strategies (Richardson, Lanis, & Taylor, 2015). According to Ayoola and Ogechukwu (2018), financially distressed firms would try to make new deals with at least one of the firm's creditors. Avramov, Chordia, Jostova, and Philipov (2013) argued that firms in distress run the risk of losing clients, partners, and even key personnel because managers will spend more time dealing with default issues rather than working to increase the value of the company.

2.1.2 Tax Aggressiveness

Tax aggressiveness was presented by Hanlon and Heitzman (2010) as activities close to the end of a continuum of tax avoidance behavior that range from lawful tax planning to investments in rather illegitimate tax shelters. Different measures of tax aggressiveness have been used in the prior literature (Lee, Dobiyski, & Minton, 2015). In this study, tax aggressiveness was measured using the cash effective tax rate, which is the ratio of total tax expenses to pre-tax income (Phillips & Regois, 2009). Effective tax rate was examined by Khaoula and Ayed (2013) and Seyram and Holy (2014) as a measure of tax planning that reduces a business's tax obligation without necessarily lowering its accounting income.

In the views of Inua (2018), cash effective tax rate is the tax rate that considers only taxes that are paid into the account, excluding deferred taxes and long-term analysis. Since effective tax rates offers a convenient summary statistic of the cumulative impacts of different tax incentives and corporate tax rate changes, it has been frequently used by policy-makers and interest groups as a tool to draw conclusions about corporate tax systems (Kern & Morris, 1992; Gupta & Newberry, 1997).

2.1.3 Board Ownership

Directors' shareholding is the percentage of a company's shares owned by its directors. According to Jensen (1993), many issues arise when a corporate firm's director do not own a significant proportion of the shares. In the first instance, directors' incentives to pursue the interests of shareholders will be threatened and such will negatively impact firms' financial

health (Simpson & Gleason 1999). Therefore, Jensen & Meckling (1976) suggest that corporate decisions that supports share ownership of directors in a bid to align the interests of the directors with shareholders becomes very important. Both agency and the information imbalance approaches can be employed to explain board ownership. The agency approach sees board ownership as a means of reducing agency conflicts, whereas the information imbalance approach sees board ownership as a mechanism for reducing information imbalance between insiders and outsiders through disclosure of information within the company. Therefore, increased board equity ownership can be employed to overcome such problems that exist in the firm.

2.1.4 Tax Aggressiveness and Financial Distress

Since a firm needs working capital to finance its activities while in financial distress, management will attempt to find several means to keep operations running which could include borrowing. Debt is one type of external funding that appeals to managers because of the tax benefits it provides. Interest costs associated with debt financing lowers taxable income, notwithstanding, higher debt burdens on the business. However, financially distressed firms may be confronted with the difficulties of accessing external funds and as a result, they will be motivated to engage in aggressive tax planning as a substitute for the expensive source of external funding from lenders (Law & Mills, 2015).

Till date, debate on the impact of financial distress on tax aggressiveness is still ongoing. Warsini et al. (2018) and Brondolo (2009) declared that financial distress has a positive effect on tax aggressiveness and noted that if the risk of bankruptcy is high enough, the company will engage in aggressive tax avoidance and will not be wary about the risk of a tax audit. Putri and Anis (2017) and Saputra and Asyik (2017) affirmed that financial distress has a positive impact on tax avoidance, noting that increased financial pressure on a firm lead to an increase in corporate tax avoidance actions. Particularly, the views of Richardson, Lanis, and Taylor (2015) revealed that financial distress has a positive relationship with tax avoidance especially during the global financial crisis era. Hence, we propose our first hypothesis as follows:

H₀₁: Tax aggressiveness has a positive and significant effect on financial distress

2.1.5 Tax Aggressiveness and Financial Distress: Role of Board Ownership

Firms that experience financial distress tend to engage in aggressive tax avoidance. According to Rani (2017), such unlawful practices are geared towards reducing cash outflows and tax expense. Richardson et al. (2015), Putri and Anis (2017), Meilia and Adnan (2017), and Saputra et al. (2017) firmly supported this view by successfully demonstrating that financial distress positively influences tax avoidance. In their opinions, corporate firms experiencing financial distress will act aggressively to reduce tax liabilities, improve funds for investment purposes and maintain the excellent images of the firms. However, Hanifah and Agus (2013) suggested that higher board ownership and prevention of information asymmetry between agent and principal should be considered in an attempt to constrain tax aggressive practices – a hallmark of good corporate governance.

In line with this, Rosidy and Rahadi (2019) argued that greater business oversight results from higher percentage of board ownership, therefore management will exercise greater caution and transparency towards tax-aggressive behavior. Further, Rani (2017), Octaviani and Sofie (2018),

Putri and Anis (2017) all suggested that higher proportion of board ownership in a company can prevent managers from becoming excessively tax aggressive. The information provided by the company will be more accurate and have more quality so much so that the possibility of aggressively managing tax burden tends to be small. Hence, we propose our second hypothesis as follows:

Ho₂: The effect of board ownership on the relationship between tax aggressiveness and financial distress is significant and negative.

2.2 Theoretical Framework - Agency Theory

This study is anchored on the agency theory. Basically, the theory stipulates the conflicts of interest that arise due to shifts in the interest of managers from that of the shareholders. Cruz, Gómez-Mejía, and Becerra (2010) observed that managers do act in their own interest, contrary to the interest of the firm and the shareholders due to poor monitoring. Within the context of the theory, corporate governance principles are vital in ensuring that the interest of the principal and agent aligns with the overall objective of the organisation. This theory specifies that manager use their discretionary powers as a cover up or decide on issues that suit their interests. They are usually more interested in short-term gains at the expense of the long-term goals of the shareholders.

The principal–agency problem can be greatly reduced through close monitoring and supervision alongside the creation of better incentives to motivate managers. This has become very necessary because firms operate in a highly competitive environment which influences the perception of managers to take decisions that are complex and risky to remain relevant. In corroborating this view, Smith and Stulz (1995) observed that agency issues have greatly influenced managers in taking risky decisions (in form of aggressive tax avoidance) and hedging in the field of corporate risk management.

2.3 Empirical Review

Ratih, Sutrisno, Endang (2020) examined the correlation between financial distress, earnings management and tax aggressiveness moderated by corporate governance using a population of manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. The purposive sampling method employed included 212 firms with complete information. Multiple regression technique which was used to test the formulated hypotheses and the results revealed that financial distress and real earnings management positively influenced tax aggressiveness, but the proportion of independent commissioners weakens the relationship. Pernamasari, Purwaningsih, Tanjung and Rahayu (2019) examined the effect of good corporate governance and financial distress prediction on Indonesian stock prices measured as stock prices obtained one week after the financial statements were released. The proxies for good corporate governance in this study included board of commissioners, and numbers of independent commissioners, business commissioners, and audit accountants while Altman Z-Score was used as the dependent variable. The result obtained using logistic regression technique showed that good corporate governance and prediction of financial distress had a significant positive effect on stock prices.

Luqman, Hassan, Tabasum, Khakwani and Irshad, (2018) studied the possibility of financial distress in the face of corporate governance structures from the Pakistani perspective. The study examined the effect of voluntary adoption of corporate governance mechanisms on financial distress. Based on a sample of 52 firms of the non-financial sector of Karachi Stock Exchange over a 10-year period, the logistic regression technique showed that blockholder ownership, director ownership and audit committee had a negative and significant effect on financial distress. Edwards, Schwab & Shevlin (2013) investigated financial constraints and the incentive for tax planning at both the macroeconomic and firm-specific level. The authors predicted that as external funds became costlier (i.e., increased financial constraints) firms would take actions to increase internally-generated funds via tax planning. Measuring financial constraints based on change in GDP and bank lending tightening and firm-specific measures, the study findings revealed that firms facing financial constraints exhibited lower cash effective tax rates which they based on capital structure trade-off theory.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design and Study Sample

This study employed ex-post facto research design with a population of one hundred and six (106) non-finance firms listed on the floor of the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) over the period between 2013 and 2022. Krejcie and Morgan, (1970) sample size computation was used to obtain a balanced panel data sample of 84 non-financial firms. However, after excluding firms with incomplete financial data within the period of under review, a final sample size of 59 firms was obtained (590 firm-year observations). Additionally, in examining whether board ownership moderates the relationship between tax aggressiveness and financial distress, the moderated logistic regression technique was used due to the dichotomous nature of the dependent variable ('0' for firms that fall within the financially healthy zone and '1' for firms that fall within the financially distress zone).

3.2 Measuring Financial Distress

In order to compute for financial distress firms, the Altman's Z-score model was employed. This model was used because it is a popular and widely acceptable measure of financial distress and corporate default prediction. Therefore, this study focuses on the possibility of financial distress taken as Altman's Z-Score. A summarized guideline for determining the financial position of the firm at the end of each fiscal year is presented below:

Table 1 - Altman Guidelines

Situations	Z-Score	Position
Likely to experience bankruptcy and financial distress	< 1.9	Financial Distress
Distress may or may not impend	1.9 to 2.9	Not Sure
Unlikely to experience financial distress	> 2.9	Financial Healthiness

Source: Shahwan (2015)

From table 1, firms with Z-Score that lies below 1.9 fall into the financial distressed zone with probability of failing in two years' time; for firms with Z-Score values lying between 1.9 and 2.9, their financial strength cannot be determined therefore their failure is difficult to predict. However, the Z-scores value above 2.9 indicates firms that are in 'a very healthy' zone and financial failure is unlikely to occur over the next two years. For the purpose of this study, we used a sample which constitutes firms that lie within the financial distress and financial healthy

zones. Furthermore, we follow the lead of Shahwan (2015) and Parkinson (2018) and modified their models to reflect the following econometric equation:

$$FDIST_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CETR_{it} + \beta_2 BOWN * CETR_{it} + \beta_3 NUMS_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

Where:

FDIST	=	Financial Distress
CETR	=	Cash Effective Tax Rate
BOWN	=	Board Ownership
NUMS	=	Number of Subsidiary
β_0	=	Constant
β_1 - β_3	=	Slope Coefficient
u	=	Stochastic disturbance
i	=	i th firm
t	=	time period

3.2 - Operationalization of Study Variables

Table 1 – Definition of Variables

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Acronym</i>	<i>Definition</i>	<i>Source</i>
Financial Distress	FDIST	Altman (1968) Financial Distress Model	Deslandes, Fortin, and Landry, (2020)
Cash Effective Tax	CETR	computed in percentage as income tax paid in cash flow statement divided by profit before tax	Octaviani and Sofie, 2019; Edwards, Schwab, and Shevlin, (2016)
Board Ownership	BOWN	computed in percentages as directors' direct and indirect shares divided by outstanding shares	Minnick and Noga, (2010)
Number of Subsidiary	NUMS	Measured as the total number of subsidiaries/outlets owned by the firm at the given time	Boussaidi and Hamed, (2015)

Authors' Computation (2023)

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

To examine the moderating role of board ownership on the relationship between effective tax rate and financial distress likelihood, we first computed some pre-regression statistical values - descriptive statistics. Descriptive statistics gives insight into the nature of the firms in the sample of the study as shown in the table 2.

Table 2 - Descriptive Statistics

Variables	observations	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
FDIST	590	0.599022	0.490396	0	1
CETR	590	24.58748	86.56114	-399.24	1229.79
BOWN	590	0.117741	0.191062	0	1.1619
NUMS	590	1.474847	3.585946	0	29

Authors' Computation

From table 2, it is obvious that on average, 60% constitute observation of firms in financial distress in relation to Z scores while 40% constitute observations of firms in financial healthy zones. On average, we find that cash effective tax rate is 24.59 with a standard deviation of 86.56 and minimum and maximum values of -399 and 1229.79 respectively. The cash effective tax rate

of about 25% means the sampled firms practice tax aggressiveness in the period under review as it is less than the statutory rate of 30% fixed by the Federal Government of Nigeria. For the moderating variable of board ownership, the result in the table 2 revealed that on average board ownership is 0.12 with a standard deviation of 0.19 and the control variable result shows that number of subsidiaries is 1 on average, indicating that the firms in the sample operated at least one (1) subsidiary during the period under investigation.

4.2 Correlation Analysis

As shown in Table 3, the Pearson correlation matrix of the summarized panel data of the listed non-financial firms in Nigeria revealed that there is positive relationship between cash effective tax rate (CETR), board ownership (BOWN) and financial distress (FDIST).

Table 3 - Pearson Correlation Matrix

	FDIST	CETR	BOWN	NUMS
FDIST	1.0000			
CETR	0.1954	1.0000		
BOWN	0.2132	-0.3115	1.0000	
NUMS	0.1542	0.4877	-0.2569	1.0000

Source: Researchers' Computation

However, negative correlation exists between board ownership (BOWN) and cash effective tax rate (CETR) as well as between board ownership (BOWN) and number of subsidiaries (NUMS). The matrix shows that all the variables chosen for the study are not perfectly correlated as none of the Pearson coefficients exceeded 0.8 as recommended by Kennedy (2008).

4.3 Regression Estimates

Table 4 shows the results obtained from the moderated logistic regression model employed to test the role of ownership structure on the relationship between tax aggressiveness and financial distress likelihood. The results indicate a 7% (Pseudo R² value of 0.07) variation in dependent variable have been caused by variations in the independent and control variables.

Table 4 - Moderated Logistic Regression Estimates (Marginal Effect)

Variables	Cash Effective Tax Rate	Cash Effective Tax * Board Ownership	Number of Subsidiary
Coef	-0.001	0.004	0.064
z_Stat	(-2.74)	(2.84)	(6.36)
Prob_z	{0.006} **	{0.005} **	{0.000} *
Likelihood Ratio (LR) = 71.52, Prob. = 0.0000			
R-Square (Pseudo) = 0.0652			
Sensitivity = 94%			
Specificity = 10%			
Overall = 61%			

Note: () and {} contains t-statistics and respective probabilities

Where: ** represents 5% & * represent 1% level of statistical significance

Judging from the model goodness of fit as captured by the likelihood ratio (71.52) with the corresponding probability value 0.0000 at 1% statistically significant level, the entire model is deemed fit and can be employed for discussion and policy recommendations. For specificity and sensitivity test, the classification table reveals that 409 cases were predicted correctly with 94%

sensitivity accuracy in a case of 753 that fell into the group of financially distressed firms. Further, the table reveal that with 10% specificity accuracy, 34 out of 61 cases that fell into the group of healthy firms during the period under review were predicted correctly. The model is free from any significant bias, therefore it can be employed for interpretation and policy recommendations due to its overall accuracy rate that stood at roughly 61% during the period under consideration.

As shown in table 4, it is obvious that the likelihood that increases in tax aggressiveness will affect financial distress is negative and statistically significant at 5%. This implies that an increase in aggressive tax practices (reduced cash effective tax rate) will probably reduce financial distress situation (increased Z-score). Hence, this study opines that on average, marginal decrease in effective tax rate will act as a good recovery tool which obviously suggest that an aggressive tax policy system can be activated as a good upscaling devise to reduce financial distress. Therefore, hypothesis one which states that tax aggressiveness has a positive significant likelihood effect on financial distress is supported and its alternate rejected.

However, with the introduction of board ownership as a moderator, the result show that the financial status of the firms will experience a reversal, indicating that tax aggressive firms with relatively higher board ownership policy will most likely be plunged into financial distress. Therefore, hypothesis two which states that the moderated likelihood effect of board ownership on the relationship between tax aggressiveness and financial distress is significantly negative is equally supported and its alternate rejected. Result from the moderation analysis is inconsistent with the studies of Richardson et al, (2015); and Edwards et al, 2013 who found that management risky strategies and tax avoidance practices will likely drag the firm into financial distress noting that financially-distressed firms have less liquidity for tax rates; hence a significant relationship exists between financial distress and tax planning (Edwards et al, 2013). However, we find consistency with the studies of Law & Mills (2015) who noted that lower effective tax rate will likely lead to recovery from financial distress.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

Financial distress is so undeserving that accounting and financial scholars throughout the world have tried to find methods to predict it occurrence. The onset of the financial crisis in the U.S. economy together with the global financial crisis at the beginning of the third millennium which was due to integration and interdependence of the global economy in recent decades and its spread to the other global economies have resulted in the most significant event. Findings of this study, conducted within the Nigerian context, depict mixed and salient situations. The result underscores the fact that managers may become more aggressive in their tax planning activities in order to improve cash flow which may subtly be a temporary bailout strategy from financial distress situations. Hence, based on the result obtained the study recommend that tax authorities and tax regulatory bodies will need to develop indicators capable of detecting financially distressed firms since managers of such firms may be tempted to evade tax – an action that is detrimental to government revenue generation policy.

Also, this study recommends that while practising aggressive tax activities within the ambit of the law, equity ownership of the board of directors should be reviewed or perhaps be set at optimal level as large board ownership will likely turn the status of the firm to a worsening situation. Concerned policy makers may reduce the volume of board ownership while

maintaining an aggressive tax policy approach to avoid financial distress. The outcome of this study will assist stakeholders in keeping track of firm business activities, reduce the risk of failure, and help firms' management make effective decisions.

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